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Analysis of Rainfall Trends in Semi-arid Hisar District, Haryana

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ABSTRACT

One of the most major challenges to socioeconomic survival is declining and erratic rainfall. This paper presents an analysis of rainfall trends in Hisar district of Haryana. Hisar's climate is impacted by its placement on the edge of south-west monsoon coverage area. The monthly and seasonal trends were analysed using data from three meteorological observatories in Hisar District: Hisar, Hansi, and Adampur. The district's rainfall characteristics were determined using historical rainfall data from 1974 to 2018 (Hisar and Hansi Stations) and 2009 to 2018 (Adampur Station). The mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation and skewness of monthly and annual rainfall were assessed to determine rainfall variability. The average annual rainfall in the district shows an inconsistent pattern, with increases and decreases in different years. Because Hisar's economy is mostly dependent on agriculture, high fluctuation in rainfall and unpredictability poses serious economic challenges for the district.

Key Words: Rainfall, Monsoon, Mean Monthly Rainfall, Trend Analysis, Hisar, Haryana.

Introduction

Weather and climate-related extreme occurrences bring a variety of issues. Water resource challenges are mostly tied to physical environments, with socioeconomic sectors coming in second. It has a direct or indirect impact on our ecosystem, cropping system, people's lives, and society's livelihood (Sharma, et al., 2021). Water is utilised in a variety of industries, including transportation, power, manufacturing, and agriculture, as well as for home consumption. Rainfall is the most essential supply of water in any area, and it has a significant impact on agriculture. The success or failure of a crop in an agricultural country like India is mainly dependent on the country's rainfall pattern. India's agriculture productivity is mainly reliant on monsoon rainfall patterns. In India, the monsoon is the primary source of water (Tiwari and Singh, 2020).

Precipitation is an important aspect of the hydrologic cycle, and variations in its pattern have a direct impact on the region's water resources. The pattern of demands especially from agriculture, the spatial and temporal distribution of drainage, soil moisture and groundwater reserves would all be affected by changes in rainfall quantity and frequency (Dore, 2005).

Monsoon rainfall is very variable and often random over long periods of time, according to most of the studies undertaken in India during the previous four decades, particularly taking into consideration the whole of India (Attri & Tyagi 2010). Monsoon rainfall across India has decreased by 4.5 per cent in recent decades (1979–2006) compared to 1949–1978 (Ranade et al. 2008). Rainfall forecast at various temporal

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and spatial scales has become a significant input for planners and policymakers alike, as well as farmers, in order to avoid losses (Singh, Mohandas & Kumar, 2015). In the light of the above discussion, the purpose of this paper is to investigate the rainfall patterns in the Hisar district of Haryana. Haryana's western agro-climatic area and Hot Arid Ecological regions are represented by Hisar. It has a hot summer and a cool winter. Almost every year, the region suffers from lack of moisture. Normally, it extends for eight months of the year, with the exception of the monsoon season (June-September), when potential demand exceeds rainfall.

Materials and Methods

In the present study the rainfall data has been collected for three meteorological observatories located at Hisar, Hansi and Adampur in Hisar District, Haryana. The data has been obtained from Indian Meteorological Center, Chandigarh. For the Hisar and Hansi stations, the data has been obtained from 1974 to 2018. However, due to lack of relevant data for Adampur station the data has been used for 2009 to 2018 time period. The annual rainfall data is evaluated, and statistical parameters have been applied to investigate the annual rainfall trends for the concerned time period. To analyze the relation between monthly and seasonal rainfall, the four statistical parameters involved are: Mean, Standard Deviation, Co-efficient of Variation and Co-efficient of Skewness. Following are the formulas used for the aforementioned statistical parameters:

$$\text{Mean } (X_{\text{avg}}) = \sum X_i / n$$

$$\text{Standard Deviation } (\tilde{A}) = [\sum (X_i - X_{\text{avg}})^2 / (n-1)]^{1/2}$$

$$\text{Co-efficient of Variation } (C_v) = 100 \times (\tilde{A} / X_{\text{avg}})$$

$$\text{Co-efficient of Skewness } (C_s) = (1 / \tilde{A}^3) \times [(N / (N^2 - 3N + 2)) \times \sum (X_i - X_{\text{avg}})^3]$$

In the above formulae,

X = Rainfall data (in mm)

i = 1, 2, 3 upto "n"

n = Time period (number of years)

N = Total number of years

Monthly rainfall data was used to calculate yearly and seasonal temporal patterns. In addition, for each month, the excess and deficient years were determined. The probability of seasonal excess/deficient rainfall is determined when each month's rainfall is excess/deficient. Monthly rainfall series are used to identify excess/deficient years for a certain month, and excess/deficient years are counted according to these excess/deficient years.

Results and Discussion

Hisar's climate is impacted by the fact that it is located on the edges of the south-west monsoon zone. It is characterized as an arid zone and has a tropical monsoon climate. The four seasons that the district endures throughout the year are summer, south-west monsoon, post-monsoon and winter. From late June to mid-September, the south-west monsoon, often known as the summer monsoon, brings rain. With the

exception of a few rainy spells generated by westerly depressions (western disturbances), the period from October through next June is mainly dry. The summers have high temperatures and are humid, whilst the winters are cold. The climate of the district is characterised by dryness, temperature oscillations and a lack of rainfall. The South West Monsoon season running from June to September receives 75 to 80 per cent of yearly rainfall, with a 50 per cent coefficient of variation. The average annual rainfall is roughly 450 millimetres, with 133.4 millimetres in July and 116.2 millimetres in August. In September, the average monthly rainfall is 54.5 millimetres, whereas in June, the average monthly rainfall is 49.8 millimetres. The average rainfall during the typical monsoon season is 283 mm. Rainfall tends to rise from the southwest to the northeast in the district.

Monthly and Annual Rainfall Features:

Annual rainfall data and monthly data from three separate stations in the Hisar district, namely Hisar, Hansi, and Adampur, have been evaluated, and the variation in distribution over the area has been studied. Monthly rainfall data for each year between 1974 and 2018 was used to determine the monthly mean for the time period at Hisar and Hansi observatories, whilst rainfall data for each year between 2009 and 2018 was used to calculate the monthly mean data at Adampur observatories. It can be seen that the month of July has the highest average rainfall (Table 1). The rainiest months are July, August, and September, while the driest months are November and December, with the lowest monthly mean rainfall.

Table 1: Rainfall Analysis - Hisar IMD Observatory - Monthly Rainfall (in millimeters) 1974 – 2018

Month	Mean (mm)	Standard Deviation (mm)	Coefficient of Variation	Coefficient of Skewness
January	12.14	12.22	1.00	1.57
February	18.36	21.94	1.19	1.63
March	17.25	21.43	1.24	1.57
April	15.25	26.52	1.73	3.66
May	26.33	25.26	0.95	0.92
June	65.96	353.91	5.36	0.00
July	135.7	87.64	0.64	0.98
August	120.6	81.32	0.67	0.4
September	77.94	75.94	0.97	1.69
October	11.26	29.13	2.58	3.68
November	3.06	8.51	2.78	4.97
December	5.11	8.63	1.68	2.40

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh

At Hisar IMD Observatory, the month of July has the greatest average monthly rainfall, averaging more than 135 mm. The months of July and August get the maximum average monthly rainfall (Figure 1),

September	41.12	45.82	1.11	2.27
October	3.97	11.26	2.83	0.01
November	0.67	1.96	2.93	3.11
December	1.81	4.25	2.353	0.01

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

Figure 2 depicts average monthly rainfall recorded at Hansi Observatory during 1974-2018. It shows that the monthly mean rainfall from June to September was much over 40mm. July and August have received the highest monthly mean rainfall of 89.42mm and 78.17mm respectively. October, November and December are the driest months of the year.

Figure 2: Average Monthly Rainfall Recorded at Hansi Observatory (1974 – 2018)

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

According to rainfall data recorded at Adampur Observatory between 2009 and 2018, June to September records the highest mean monthly rainfall (Table 3). July noted the highest monthly mean rainfall of 64.57 mm. At the same time, the data from Adam observatory station also highlights high monthly mean during August and September. November month with a mean monthly rainfall of zero shows complete absence of rainfall making it the driest month.

Table 3: Rainfall Analysis - Adampur IMD Observatory - Monthly Rainfall (in millimeters) 2009 – 2018

Month	Mean (mm)	Standard Deviation (mm)	Coefficient of Variation	Coefficient of Skewness
January	16.1	29.11	1.80	3.21
February	14	29.475	2.10	3.36
March	10.8	10.52	0.97	0.31
April	4.44	6.40	1.44	1.62
May	7	11.52	1.64	1.92
June	22.6	21.29	0.94	1.01
July	64.57	51.53	0.79	2.27
August	31.7	30.72	0.96	1.50
September	32.8	37.62	1.14	2.54
October	2.8	5.36	1.91	3.04
November	0	0	0	0
December	0.87	2.385	2.74	3.65

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

Figure 3: Average Monthly Rainfall in Adampur (IMD Observatory) (2009-2018)

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

January to May receive rainfall that is infrequent and highly variable ranging from 0 to 17mm monthly mean rainfall (Fig.3). To summarise, the climate of the Hisar district is characterised by high temperatures with humidity in summers whereas winters are cold, receiving an average annual precipitation of about 450 mm, which is typical of an arid environment. This rainfall is only enough to cover 15-20 per cent of yearly potential evapo-transpiration (PET) demand, resulting in a year-round water deficit (Singh et al., 2010). The rainfall trend over Hisar was examined in this study to determine the direction of change of precipitation over a period of 45 years i.e. 1974-2018.

Figure 4: Rainfall Trend in Hisar District (1974-2018)

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

The annual rainfall data for the last 45 years shows a great deal of fluctuation across time. Monsoon rains made a constant impact throughout the year. Annual rainfall varied substantially over the time, with the overall trend indicating a decrease (Figure 4). Thus implying that in the arid type of climatic conditions that characterize this region, the failure of rainfall in any month is not uncommon.

Seasonal Rainfall

The southwest monsoon, which accounts for nearly 80 per cent of total precipitation, is critical for drinking and irrigation water supplies. Climate change would have a considerable impact on agricultural output, management of water resources and the broader economy eventually, particularly during the southwest monsoon period. Water scarcity occurs in numerous areas during the non-monsoon months due to a lack of rainfall. Over a lengthy period of time, monsoon rainfall has no unified trend and is largely random in nature, especially while assessing it at a national level (Mooley and Parthasarathy, 1984). On the other hand, Kumar et al. (2013) observed pattern occurrence on a geographical scale. Even though the southwest induced monsoon season is the most important precipitation season, other seasons do have a critical

influence in a few locations. The climate of Hisar district is subtropical, semi-arid, continental, and monsoon. The south-west monsoon causes the major rainy season, which lasts from June to September. From late June to mid-September, the south west monsoon (summer monsoon) is the main source of rain in the district; except for a few occasional rains generated by westerly depressions/western disturbances, the period from October until the following June is completely dry. The summers are hot and humid, whilst the winters are moderate. The features of rainfall in the study region during the four seasons are listed below:

Pre Monsoon Season

Kripalani et al. (2003) investigated the inter-annual and decadal variability in summer monsoon rainfall over India using observational data extending from 1971 to 2001. They identified random variations in annual rainfall as well as distinct alternating epochs (lasting about three decades) of above and below normal rainfall in terms of decadal trends. The rainfall pattern through the pre-monsoon season (March to May) is significant because it aids in the planning of crop-related activities. Figure 3.5 shows Hisar district's pre-monsoon rainfall trend over the last 45 years.

Figure 5: Pre Monsoon Rainfall Trend in Hisar District (1974-2018)

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

The district received 0.85 mm of rainfall during the pre-monsoon season in 1984, which was the lowest ever recorded data. During 2007, the district received 52.73 mm rainfall, was the highest Pre Monsoon Rainfall during the same period. The data further reveals that out of total study period, 10 years have received rainfall more than 15 mm in pre monsoon season in study area. Trend lineshown in Figure.5 suggest that there is increasing trend of pre-monsoon season under the study period.

Monsoon Season

The monsoon is the seasonal onset of strong winds and precipitation in India, commonly known as the south west monsoon. Around 80 per cent of the rainfall falls during the four monsoon months (June, July, August and September), with significant geographical and temporal variations. The frequency of heavy rainfall events during the southwest monsoon is increasing in some regions of the country whereas it is decreasing throughout the winter, pre monsoon and post monsoon months (Sinha & Srivastava, 1999). The monsoon rainfall trend in the study area is depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Monsoon Rainfall Trend in Hisar District (1974-2018)

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

The monsoon period (June to September) receives the majority of rainfall in a year. All the years except 1987 have received rainfall more than 20mm per year with majority of years having rainfall more than 40mm (Figure 6). The year 1987 received only 17mm rainfall which was the lowest rainfall ever received during 45 of study period. During the same period there were three years i.e. 1976, 1995 and 2008 when rainfall received was more than 120mm. During 1988, 165 mm rainfall was received in monsoon season which was the highest during the same study period. However, the trend line as shown in Figure 6 suggest declining trend in receipt of rainfall during the monsoon season.

Post monsoon season

The months from October to December are called as post monsoon season or northern monsoon season. According to Wisser et al. (2008), there has been a large drop in groundwater storage in western Nepal over the decades of 2001–2010 and 1991–2000, owing to a significant post-monsoon desiccation tendency. Irrigation in OND grew by 210 mm mon^{-1} from 2000 to 2014. This loss of ground water might

be linked to water usage for irrigation in North India.

Figure 7: Post Monsoon Rainfall Trend in Hisar District (1974-2018)

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

Figure 7 depicts the post monsoon rainfall trends over 45 years in study area. The years with the least rainfall during the post-monsoon season are 1974, 1976, 1993, 1999, 2000, 2010, 2011 and 2017 that was less than 1 mm only. During 1998, Hisar district received 55.87 mm rainfall which is indeed highest recorded rainfall in the time period. The data further reveals that out of 45 years, only 7 years have recorded rainfall more than 5 mm and remaining years received rainfall less than 5 mm. The trend line as shown in Figure 7 reveals slight decrease trend in post monsoon rainfall during this period.

According to Chen et al. (2019), the drying of the post-monsoon season corresponds to a quicker shift from the rainy to the dry season, indicating a change in the local circulation over South Asia. Previous study has linked the Arctic Oscillation's (AO) inter-annual fluctuations and decadal trend toward negative phases to winter droughts in North India, resulting in a local mass flux circulation with the descending branch. There is also a decrease in post-monsoon rainfall in the research area.

Winter Season

The Indian winter monsoon is known as the Western Disturbances because they are the primary source of precipitation including snowfall, for the North Indian territory during the winter months. Extratropical storm systems that begin in the Arctic, Mediterranean and Middle East proceed to Afghanistan, Pakistan and India. They are crucial for India's Rabi cropping season because they keep the soil hydrated.

Figure.8: Winter Rainfall Trend in Hisar District (1974-2018)

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

Figure 8 shows the study area's winter rainfall trends over the last 45 years. The driest winter season came in 2016, when the research region received barely 2 millimetres of rain. The research area received 32.02 mm of rain in 2013, the greatest amount ever recorded throughout the study period. The data also shows that rainfall totaled more than 10 mm during the course of the 18-year observation period. The amount of rainfall received per year was less than 10 mm in the majority of years, indicating a decreasing tendency in rainfall throughout the winter season. In the research area, the decreasing trend in winter rainfall has adverse impact on soil moisture for producing Rabi crops.

The above study indicates the wide fluctuations in rainfall distribution throughout the study period. It also draws attention to the region's unusual and unpredictable rainfall patterns. Rainwater availability in the district is limited, and it must be kept in water bodies or in the form of ground water for use during the dry season to ensure that the livelihood and requirements of the rural population are met. Rainfall failure is a disaster for areas with little or insufficient rainfall. Rainfall failure causes ponds and wells to dry up, resulting in a shortage of water for agricultural and domestic use. It also implies a lack of animal fodder and, in many cases, agricultural failure. Droughts and water scarcity are common in the study area due to the significant unpredictability of rainfall.

Rainfall Behavior in Excess and Deficient Years

The protracted dry spell that follows the short rainy season accelerates evaporation, causing soil moisture depletion (Inderjeet, 2005). The amount of rain that falls each year is insufficient to keep the soil hydrated all the years. Droughts happen when the amount of rain received is less than projected. Drought is defined as a drop in rainfall of more than 25 per cent compared to average rainfall in the area (Kumar, 2007). Drought causes crops to begin to shrivel (Rama, 1978). Agricultural drought occurs when soil moisture is insufficient for agricultural growth, while meteorological drought occurs when rainfall is less than 25 per

cent of average. Reservoirs, lakes, streams, and rivers dry up when there is a lack of surface and ground water, resulting in hydrological dryness (Kumar, 2007). In India, severe droughts are caused by a mixture of all three types of droughts (Pangare et al., 2006).

The following rainfall-related criteria have been specified by the Indian Meteorological Department which defines:

- Excess Rainfall : +20 per cent or more than the average of past 70 to 100 years
- Normal Rainfall : +19 per cent to -19 per cent of the average of past 70 to 100 years
- Deficient Rainfall : -20 per cent to -59 per cent of the average of past 70 to 100 years
- Scanty Rainfall : -60 per cent or less than the average of past 70 to 100 years.

The average rainfall in Hisar district for time period 1974 to 2018 was calculated to be 450 mms. During the monsoon season, the area receives about 85 per cent of its yearly rainfall (Groundwater Management Studies in Hisar district, 2017). Table 4 depicts the rainfall behaviour of the research area in terms of monthly excess and deficient (1974-2018). The month of July and August has the highest excess monthly rainfall years ranging from 123 mm to 408 mm (Table 4).

Table 4: Monthly Deviation in Rainfall Behaviour (1974 – 2018).

Month	Excess Years		Deficient Years	
	No. of Years	Range (mm)	No. of Years	Range (mm)
January	18	14.5 - 51.6	22	0.2 - 10.7
February	16	18.1 - 89.7	29	0.4 - 16.2
March	16	17.9 - 88	29	0.2 - 13.5
April	12	23.2 - 150.3	33	0.7 - 14.2
May	17	34.5 - 88.6	28	0.2 - 26
June	14	69.3 - 296.5	31	11.3 - 64.9
July	23	142.8 - 407.9	22	1 - 132.2
August	20	123 - 292.6	25	9.7 - 115.1
September	17	84.9 - 364.2	28	1 - 62.3
October	8	11.7 - 151.4	37	0.3 - 9.4
November	8	3.9 - 52.9	37	0.1 - 2.8
December	13	5.5 - 33.8	31	0.3 - 4.8

Source: India Meteorological Center, Chandigarh.

On the other side, October, November and December have the highest deficient years with rainfall ranging from 0.1mm to 9.4 mm.

Figure 9: Monthly Deviation in Rainfall Behaviour (1974 – 2018).

Source: Based on Table 3.4.

It is observed in Figure 9 that overall the numbers of deficient months are higher than that of excess months, representing the shortfall of rainfall as well as high variability in rainfall in the district. Between 1974 and 2018, the district's average annual rainfall reveals an intermittent behavior, with increase and decrease in different years. The years with excessive rainfalls witnessed rainfall of 600 mm to 800 mm while years with deficient rainfall witnessed rainfall of 100 mm to 300 mm.

Conclusion

The considerable variation of Hisar district's rainfall is its most distinguishing attribute. Hisar's economy is primarily based on agriculture. Because of the district's semi-arid climate and lack of a perennial river, agriculture is heavily reliant on rainfall. As a result of the foregoing analysis, the study area's monthly mean rainfall in June, July, August, and September is considerably over 40 mm. With 89.42 mm and 78.17 mm, respectively, July and August had the highest monthly mean rainfall. October, November and December are the driest months of the year, with monthly mean rainfall of less than 2 mm. Rainfall is limited and highly variable, especially from January to May, with monthly mean rainfall varying from 0 to 17 mm. The month of July has the most precipitation. November, and December are the months with the least rainfall. Overall, the study shows a lack of rainfall throughout months and a considerable degree of variability in the annual rainfall distribution. The absence of rain has a significant impact on groundwater replenishment, which has important implications for the hydrological cycle and agricultural productivity.

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